

EFFECTS OF AUDIO-TACTILE FLOOR AUGMENTATION ON PERCEPTION AND ACTION DURING WALKING: PRELIMINARY RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

Two pilot experiments have been conducted to investigate the influence of auditory and underfoot tactile cues respectively on perception and action during walking. The first experiment shows that illusory tactile perception can be generated, biased by the intensity of auditory cues in the low-frequency region. The second experiment suggests that non-visual foot-level augmentation may influence the gait cycle in normally able subjects. In the respective limits of significance, taken together both experiments suggest that the introduction of ecological elements of augmented reality at floor level may be exploited for the development of novel multimodal interfaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, multimodal interaction has become more and more relevant in human-computer interfaces. Often following an *ecological* approach, several researchers now take into consideration multiple sensory modalities that humans employ during their interactions with the surrounding environment [1] or the act of playing a traditional musical instrument [2]. From the investigation in a multimodal and ecological perspective of such consolidated everyday experiences, researchers aim at achieving seamless interaction and at enhancing the user's performance on novel interfaces, spacing from digital musical interfaces and instruments, to computer desktops, smart objects, virtual and augmented environments. In this effort, besides traditional and novel visualization paradigms, researchers are especially focusing on auditory and haptic display concepts.

Cross-modal illusions are a known phenomenon and studies can be found which investigate especially the mutual influence of auditory and haptic or vibrotactile feedback [3], ranging from perceptual assessment [4, 5] up to investigating the possible origins of auditory-vibrotactile interference [6].

Given these preliminary remarks, the act of walking represents a very attractive study case as it involves a complex integration of visual, auditory, tactile, vestibular and pro-

prioceptive cues. By often competing with parallel visual tasks, this act is generally left to the periphery of the attention, and called back to the visual focus only occasionally, or whenever a walking person is alerted by non-visual messages signaling changes in the ground characteristics (e.g. a step or a pothole).

Specifically concerning the act of walking, a few existing studies deal with the recognition of ground properties by means of auditory and vibrotactile underfoot cues [7, 8]. Several studies have investigated the possibility to influence gait patterns by using rhythmical auditory cues, especially for rehabilitation purposes [9, 10]. The role of foot-step sounds on posture has been studied in [11], while the effect of 3D audio and stereo graphics has been exploited in [12] to redirect walking in a virtual reality environment. Also, the effect of auditory startle on the avoidance of obstacles during walking has been studied in [13].

Interaction designers have recently begun to promote augmented floor interfaces as means to interactively exchange non-visual information for human navigation [8]. Among the different prototypes resulting from such concepts, interactive shoes promise to play a leading role for their function as wearable foot-floor interfaces that inherently fit to the user personal and social needs [8, 14].

For the reasons pointed above, we worked on the development of a footwear interface capable of providing ecological feedback, partially matching that experienced when real changes in the ground properties occur during walking.

In this paper, the results of two pilot experiments are described, which assess how ecological floor-augmentations may influence walking persons, with regard to both their perception of auditory and tactile cues of ground surfaces, and their walking action. These experiments have already been described briefly in [8], where the discussion is however limited to a review of the results. Specifically it will be claimed that, when walking on a flat solid floor surface while wearing our instrumented footwear, subjects with no auditory, somatosensory, vestibular or locomotion disorders:

- feel tactile cues of aggregate ground materials (e.g. gravel, underbrush, icy snow), whose perceived quality depends on the intensity of low-frequency auditory cues;
- alter their normal gait cycle if auditory-tactile feed-

Figure 1. The instrumented sandals prototype (bottom and top view) used in the experiments.

back augmentation is enabled.

Although promising, these results however need further experimental validation aimed at reinforcing their statistical validity.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The design of the software/hardware system and the stimuli used in the experiments is described hereunder.

2.1 Setup and apparatus

The wearable component of the apparatus consisted in instrumented footwear equipped with force sensors, vibrotactile transducers, and a battery-powered data acquisition board interfaced with a wireless I/O communication system. The latter allowed to send out force data, and in turn received audio signals. A host computer, communicating with the footwear by means of a mirror wireless I/O system, was responsible for processing the acquired force data and for synthesizing audio-tactile feedback in real-time.

In more detail, a pair of sport sandals with rubber soles were equipped each with two Interlink 402 force-sensing resistors and two Dayton Audio DAEX32 vibrotactile transducers. Such devices were respectively inserted/attached in/at the sole, by the forefoot and heel areas. The sandals, sized 44 of the European scale (corresponding to U.S. male size 10 1/2), could as well fit smaller foot sizes thanks to Velcro straps. Figure 1 sketches our prototype, representing the wearable front-end of the apparatus used in the experiment.

Force data coming from the sandals were acquired and passed by an Arduino Duemilanove board through serial communication to a 2.4 GHz transceiver module based on the Nordic Semiconductor nRF2401A chip. At the computer end, a symmetrical module received and forwarded the data stream to another Arduino board, communicating with the host via USB. Conversely, feedback data were

transmitted to the sandals by a RME Fireface 400 audio card through two pairs of E-MU PIPELINE wireless transceivers, one transmitter-receiver pair per stereo channel.

Thanks to the use of an optimized custom data encoding system at the interface side and low-latency audio devices, the entire system takes less than 20 ms to acquire force data and receive the corresponding synthesized feedback,¹ ensuring the perception of instantaneous interaction as that offered by our previous (wired) prototype [15].

2.2 Stimuli

The interactive feedback was produced by making use of the Sound Design Toolkit (SDT), a collection of physically-based models for real-time synthesis of ecological sound events [16]. Custom synthesizers were built on top of this package, by properly feeding the included *impact* sound model with the sensed force, as well as by tuning the parameters of higher-level synthesis engines, such as the *crumpling* model, until obtaining (based on the informal general opinion of users) auditory and tactile feedback matching that of real aggregate ground materials.

The use of audio signals for providing both auditory and vibrotactile cues is justified by the fact that the two share a common physical nature, as they consist in mechanical vibrations, moreover in an overlapping frequency range, that are perceived by humans through different senses. In this regard, the use of physically-based models whose output represents the vibrations of a resonating object, is particularly well suited.

For the first experiment two crumpling sound samples were recorded (one for the forefoot-floor and one for the heel-floor interaction), and were further enriched by mixing them with two high quality recordings of a footstep over dry leaves. The crumpling model has been previously used in a related study on interactive augmentation of neutral floors [17]. As a result we obtained two stimuli that conveyed a definite ecological impression similar to that received when walking over aggregate ground materials. The use of static recordings, as opposed to interactively synthesized signals, allowed to keep the feedback intensity constant and the stimulation repeatable during the experimental task.

Conversely, force data sensed by the instrumented sandals during walking was used to drive in real-time the crumpling and impact models, that were configured for simulating different ground materials: respectively, icy snow and mud. Thanks to the physical foundations of the SDT models, the feedback resulting from walking responded to the user's gesture in a very dynamic and realistic way.

3. EXPERIMENT 1: INFLUENCE OF AUDITORY FEEDBACK ON TACTILE PERCEPTION

We hypothesized that during a walking task augmented by auditory and vibrotactile underfoot cues reproducing virtual aggregate grounds, low-frequency intensity variations

¹ The round-trip latency was measured as the delay between the onset of an impulse at the force sensors and the arrival of the corresponding feedback signals to the excitors.

in the acoustic feedback can alter the simultaneous tactile perception.

A similar hypothesis was proposed by Guest *et al.* with regard to the hand, in a study investigating how perceived tactile roughness/moistness of real textured surfaces is influenced by spectral manipulations of the sound generated when touching such surfaces [18].

In parallel we have followed a methodology close to that proposed by Altinsoy [4] who showed that changes in sound loudness can affect the perceived force feedback while beating a virtual drum pad with the hand. According to this methodology, the vibrotactile feedback was kept constant across all trial sessions, and subjects were specifically instructed to base their judgments only on tactile information, while ignoring the sounds they heard.

3.1 Method

Twelve male and five female subjects, aged 20 to 26 years old, participated in the experiment. None of them reported any foot- or locomotion-related deficiencies.

The subjects were asked to wear the instrumented sandals and walk along a predefined path. They were informed that a change in feedback could occur halfway during each trial, meanwhile it was not disclosed to them that the vibrotactile feedback would be kept constant across the whole experiment. Only the intensity of low-frequency sound could be varied by the experimenters midway at each trial. After each trial, the subjects had to differentiate between perceived (indeed illusory) changes in the vibrotactile feedback, by providing affirmative or negative answers together with a confidence rate from 1 to 7.

Since the transducers embedded in the sandals produced at the same time sound and tactile feedback, precluding them to be segregated, then four Genelec 8020A loudspeakers were placed each at one corner of the experiment room, on rubber stands which prevented the transmission of mechanical energy to the floor. This solution allowed to vary the auditory-to-tactile feedback ratio, but it potentially enabled users to localize footstep sound sources off their feet. For this reason only the low-frequency component of the sound feedback (obtained by cutting off the signals at 162 Hz by means of 24 dB/octave filters) was routed to the loudspeakers. Additionally, these were set to point backward with respect to the center of the room, toward diffusive flat panels placed at the corners. The presence of loudspeakers in the room was motivated to the subjects by continuously playing a monophonic ecological “soundscape”, which reproduced rustle of leaves, birdsong and springing water. Overall, this arrangement prevented the subjects to localize footstep sounds out of the sandals, furthermore increasing the ecology of the scenario.

A set of stimuli corresponding to different loudspeakers levels (i.e. only affecting the low-frequency spectrum) were selected. Specifically, a reference stimulus S^{+0} producing an average loudness of 45-47 dB(A) around the room was taken as a reference, along with $S^{+6} = S^{+0} + 6$ dB and $S^{+12} = S^{+0} + 12$ dB. Notably, S^{+12} resulted in 45-48 dB(A) around the room, testifying the negligible impact of changes in the low-frequency sound feedback on the per-

Figure 2. Results of experiment 1: mean percentage of “yes” responses along with standard deviations for the *constant* couples, and differences in-between. ***: $p < 0.001$, **: $p < 0.01$, *: $p < 0.05$, NS: not significant.

Figure 3. Results of experiment 1: mean percentage of “yes” responses along with standard deviations for the *increasing* and *decreasing* couples, and differences in-between. ***: $p < 0.001$, **: $p < 0.01$, *: $p < 0.05$, NS: not significant.

ceived² loudness.

By presenting two stimuli one after the other during the same trial, either *constant* e.g. (S^{+6}, S^{+6}) or *increasing* e.g. (S^{+0}, S^{+6}) or *decreasing* e.g. (S^{+12}, S^{+0}) couples were provided. Half subjects were presented with a balanced random sequence of constant and increasing couples, both repeated four times, followed by a balanced random sequence of constant and decreasing couples, both repeated four times. The other half subjects were presented with the same two sequences in reversed order. Each subject therefore had to undergo a set of 48 trials, taking approximately 40 minutes.

3.2 Results and preliminary discussion

The results are summarized in Figures 2 and 3.

The deviation from random (line at 50%) was tested using one-proportion (two-tailed) z-tests, assuming $\alpha = 0.05$. The differences between the three sets of stimuli couples were tested with two-proportion z-tests (two-tailed and Bonferroni-adjusted $\alpha = 0.05/3$).

The mean confidence ratings amounted to around 4, indicating that there were no ceiling or floor effects, and fur-

² The A-weighting curve used for loudness evaluation is designed to provide a measure of the subjectively perceived loudness.

thermore no significant differences were found in confidence ratings among the different types of couples.

The histograms show that intensity changes of ± 12 dB create salient illusory effects on tactile perception. In parallel, variations of ± 6 dB seem to be at the “threshold of illusion”, as the percentages of affirmative answers is close to those produced when no changes occur.

Notably, several subjects described the illusion as a change in their impression of “sinking” with the feet into the ground. Similar observations have been described within the limits of changes only in the magnitude of tactile feedback by Visell *et al.*, who found that vibrations influence haptic perception of surface compliance during walking [19].

4. EXPERIMENT 2: INFLUENCE OF AUGMENTED FLOOR FEEDBACK ON GAIT CYCLE

Our experimental hypothesis was that human gait can be influenced by providing ecological audio-tactile feedback through the feet.

In a related work [17] the authors have shown that gait patterns, accounting for specific emotional intentions, are affected by ecological auditory and vibrotactile underfoot feedback, albeit not to a statistically significant degree. The results of our experiment support such previous conclusions, overall suggesting that supplying subjects which walk on a neutral, solid floor with non-visual interactive cues representing virtual grounds may have perceptual salience, however not to the point of pushing them into changing their usual walking style.

4.1 Method

Eight subjects, seven males and one female of average age 22.3 years old, participated in the experiment. Six subjects were right-handed and also considered their right foot as dominant. One subject was left-handed and one ambidextrous, also with regard to the use of feet. None of them reported any foot-sensitivity or locomotion deficiencies.

The subjects were asked to wear the instrumented sandals and walk along a figure-of-eight path in the experiment room.

Three experimental conditions were set up, corresponding to different stimuli: one control condition (N) without additional feedback, and two conditions providing artificial audio-tactile feedback simulating respectively icy snow (S) and mud (M)

The subjects were informed that a different feedback could occur at each trial. The experiment considered 8 trials for each condition, resulting in sessions of 24 randomly balanced trials, lasting about 15 minutes overall.

In order to avoid biases due to the room configuration, half of the participants started walking from one of the shorter sides of the rectangular room and the other half from the other side.

In view of the following analysis, the force data provided by the four sensors were recorded separately for each trial, with a resolution of 10 bit @ 1050 Hz per channel.

4.2 Results and preliminary discussion

The slopes in the recorded force data were analyzed to extract the following inter-onset intervals (IOIs) between foot-floor contacts: heel-to-toe for the left and right foot (respectively labeled H2TL and H2TR); right heel-to-left heel (H2H); right heel-to-left toe (H2TRL). The IOIs corresponding to the first and last steps in each trial were then discarded, as they introduced unreliable values in the measurement: indeed in such phases the subjects respectively accelerated from stance to a walking pace, and decelerated until stop.

In a first phase of the analysis, the trials in the control condition were considered as repeated measures for each subject, and the mean IOIs in each trial were used to inform a one-way repeated measures (RM) ANOVA, aimed at verifying whether the subjects walked with a regular pace when no floor augmentation was present. The obtained p-values shown in Table 1 are very high, suggesting that the subjects had a regular gait cycle in this condition. In particular, the H2TR interval appeared to be extremely regular.

H2TL	$F(7,7) = 1.36$, $p = 0.2420$
H2TR	$F(7,7) = 0.21$, $p = 0.9814$
H2H	$F(7,7) = 0.69$, $p = 0.6788$
H2TRL	$F(7,7) = 1.38$, $p = 0.2345$

Table 1. Results of experiment 2: repeated measures ANOVA in the control condition N.

Considering the above results and since the majority of the participants (six over eight) were right-handed, we performed a second RM-ANOVA on such subjects only. As shown in Table 2, the IOIs from these subjects are much more irregular, except for the H2TR interval. This may in-

H2TL	$F(7,5) = 2.30$, $p = 0.0485$
H2TR	$F(7,5) = 0.97$, $p = 0.4713$
H2H	$F(7,5) = 2.88$, $p = 0.0173$
H2TRL	$F(7,5) = 6.03$, $p = 0.0001$

Table 2. Results of experiment 2: repeated measures ANOVA for right-handed subjects in the control condition N.

dicates that only the dominant foot provides reliable data. Also, this may suggest that a confidence value $\alpha = 0.05$ can be assumed in the analysis, thus allowing to isolate the irregularities found for the right-handed subjects in the neutral condition N.

Finally, the IOIs in the three conditions N, S and M were also tested using a RM-ANOVA, considering the mean IOIs over all trials in each condition. The obtained results are shown in Table 3.

A comparison of Table 1 and 3 shows that the gait cycle was affected by the audio-tactile feedback augmentation. The effect is especially evident from the H2TR and H2H IOIs, which were the most constant ones in the control test: by assuming a confidence value $\alpha = 0.05$ as suggested

H2TL	$F(2,7) = 2.22$, $p = 0.1452$
H2TR	$F(2,7) = 3.09$, $p = 0.0775$
H2H	$F(2,7) = 3.01$, $p = 0.0815$
H2TRL	$F(2,7) = 2.58$, $p = 0.1108$

Table 3. Results of experiment 2: repeated measures ANOVA in the three conditions N, S and M.

above, the results from the H2TR and H2H intervals are indeed close to statistical significance.

However, the relatively high p-values indicate that the effect hypothesized for this experiment needs further investigation. In particular the experiment should be repeated with a larger number of subjects, as eight subjects do not guarantee the conditions to properly perform the ANOVA test.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two experiments have been presented, suggesting that ecological floor augmentations can influence the perception of vibrotactile cues underfoot and the gait cycle.

If confirmed, such results may be exploited in navigation aid applications, by providing users with informative yet non-intrusive auditory and vibrotactile underfoot cues. For instance, virtual pathways may be defined by simulating different ground materials through non-visual cues, thus helping normally sighted as well as visually-impaired persons keep the right track in complex functional spaces such as airports, railway stations and so on.

Although promising, both experiments need a more robust implementation: the former should rely on a more expressive set of stimuli, including the presentation of variable vibrotactile cues, whereas the latter promises to gain significance when considering a larger number of subjects.

The investigation of cross-modal phenomena involving auditory and tactile feedback is of great relevance for the development of general multimodal interfaces, as well as digital music interfaces. It is acknowledged that audio-tactile feedback plays a central role in the action-perception loop and enables embodiment [20]. In particular, the kinesthetic and vibrotactile feedback offered by traditional musical instruments concur to inform the sophisticated control strategies, that make experienced musicians in condition to achieve top performance levels (e.g. in terms of expressivity, precise timing, etc.) [2, 21].

With regard to the results presented in this study, on the one hand the slight perceptual amplification of somatosensory cues through controlled loudness changes in the auditory feedback (experiment 1) may contribute to optimize the use of vibrotactile actuation in digital music interfaces, resulting in the adoption of smaller and cheaper mechanical excitors; on the other hand, the provision of carefully designed vibrotactile feedback (experiment 2) may improve the performer’s embodiment and performance.

Current digital music interfaces however generally lack complex tactile feedback, if not as by-product of the interfaces’ mechanics and onboard loudspeaker vibrations.

Further research involving quantitative and qualitative evaluation is therefore needed to refine the use of such modality in future music interfaces.

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